

**STUDY ON THE EFFECTIVENESS OF E-MARKETING ON
MICRO, SMALL AND MEDIUM ENTERPRISES (MSMES)
IN B2B MARKET OF BANGALORE DISTRICT**

Dr. Y. Nagaraju* & Anil Kumar Kottani**

* Professor, Canara Bank School of Management Studies, Jnana Bharathi Campus,
Bangalore University, Karnataka

** Research Scholar, Canara Bank School of Management Studies, Jnana Bharathi
Campus, Bangalore University, Karnataka

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Abstract:

This paper on e-marketing effectiveness on Micro, Small and Medium Enterprises basically deals with the analysis through a study on the importance of e-marketing tools for MSMEs primarily focusing on level of e-marketing usage in MSMEs, its benefits or advantages as well as the factors influencing the use of e-marketing by MSMEs. Available material on the effectiveness or impact of using this powerful channel of e-marketing and its tools in the marketing activities of MSMEs have been studied in the international and Indian context to present a concrete view on the study undergone for the benefit of future research on this phenomenal topic of interest. The paper highlights evidence on current usage of e-marketing among MSMEs of Bangalore District and its benefits followed by factors that influence their decision to adopt the e-marketing in their businesses. Although e-marketing has achieved tremendous experience, reach and growth worldwide and also in India very little study has been done to examine this phenomenon especially among MSMEs of Bangalore District. It is therefore important to get an insight into how MSMEs are currently using e-marketing, its benefits to them and the factors that influence the adoption e-marketing in their businesses. In order to achieve these objectives, the researcher uses quantitative study in order provide in-depth description on its current usage level, its benefits and the factors that influence their decision to adopt e-marketing in their business. The paper concludes that e-marketing is one of the highly effective and beneficial channels of marketing today to local businesses especially to MSMEs in the B2B market of Bangalore District.

Key Words: E-Marketing, MSMEs, Internet & B2B

Introduction:

E-marketing is considered to be the most happening phenomena in the world today particularly because of its potential to radically change the way the business is conducted today offering a competitive edge ever in the history and a gateway to the world market. An eruptive growth of e-marketing across the globe in the last two decades has opened up a vast area thereby providing innumerable opportunities for businesses, in particular MSMEs to make up their businesses to reach the world market to promote their products and services which would have been impossible with the conventional traditional marketing. There is an immense potential for MSMEs to effectively trap this powerful tool of marketing to grow bigger and bigger with higher productivity and competitive edge. E-marketing is the only means through which this sector can extend their business across the countries at minimal cost. Only E-marketing has that potential to empower the MSMEs to compete with larger firms in the global market. In a country like India wherein MSME sector is considered to be a backbone of Indian Economy. The Sector consisting of 36 million units, as of today, provides employment to over 80 million persons. The Sector through more than 6,000 products contributes about 8% to GDP besides 45% to the total manufacturing output and 40% to the exports from the country. The MSME sector has the potential to spread industrial growth across the country and can be a major partner in the process of inclusive growth (Ref: MSME at a glance 2016 published by Ministry of MSME). By considering the facts and figures of the significance of this sector it is evident that the contribution of MSMEs to the economy of India is vital and it can never be underemphasized. Although the e-marketing has experienced tremendous growth worldwide including India, according to the researcher a very little research has been conducted to examine its phenomena especially among MSMEs in India particularly the MSMEs in the B2B market of Bangalore District. It is therefore of importance that insight be gained into how MSMEs are currently using the e-marketing and its level of usage among MSMEs in B2B market, the factors that influence their decision to adopt the e-marketing in business and its benefits for establishing some practical guidelines of its usage for the future.

Importance of E-Marketing to MSMEs:

E-Marketing creates a platform for firms to market their products or services with Internet medium which includes various e-marketing tools viz., emailing, websites, online banners, portals, blogs, social network sites etc., Basically e-marketing today serves all the needs of marketing which otherwise was done traditionally

over the years. In spite of these benefits of doing marketing electronically, some companies especially among MSMEs are not willing to engage in e-marketing activities and do not want to spend extra effort on internet platforms as they are skeptical about its efficiency. However, it must be emphasized that, the e-marketing equips owners/sales managers of MSMEs to effectively market their products or services compared to traditional forms of marketing.

In this modern age of business, e-marketing platform ensures the spreading of awareness of companies' products and services, successful generation of business leads, improves company brand and image, increases the market reach, ensures the competitiveness of companies etc., This is because e-marketing enhances companies selling abilities through the optimum utilization of e-marketing tools. Today E-marketing has become a preferred choice of all businesses globally and considering how widely it is being used today by businesses in different sectors or industries attest to its reliability and efficiency. E-marketing provides MSMEs with a platform where they can explore business opportunities. This platform equips and enables MSMEs to position themselves to take advantage of greater opportunities and growth. Growth is life-line of any businesses; otherwise competition will grow more and overtake them. Therefore, it is imperative to invest time and resources in the continuous growth of business to ensure a firm's survival in the competitive business environment. It is important for firms to struggle for continuous growth keeping the aim of increasing or simply maintaining their sales and profits levels, to ensure their survival (Claver, Andreu and Quer, 2006). Lately, E-marketing has become a yardstick for growth and competitiveness and it is imperative on any firms and more specifically to MSMEs.

E-Marketing Tools:

- ✓ **Website:** Website is a show-case of company profile. It provides the information about company's business port-folio, products, services etc., to the entire world as 24*7 marketing platform to source the company's information and contact.
- ✓ **Search Engine Marketing:** Search Engine Marketing is basically a tool to market company products or services by placing ads on search engines like Google, Yahoo, Bing etc., Unlike traditional online advertising, advertisers pay only when users actually click on an ad. There are two types of search engine marketing: - 1 Pay-Per Click 2 Search Engine Optimization (SEO)
- ✓ **E-Mail Marketing:** Email marketing is a method of communication with business prospects/customers using the e-mail id's of personnel/companies to exchange the marketing information about product or service or for soliciting feedback from customer about a product or service through Email. Email addresses of customers and prospective customer may be collected or purchased.
- ✓ **Banner Advertisement:** Unlike the advertisements placed traditionally in newspapers, magazines, hoarding. Online banner is a placement of ads on web pages.
- ✓ **Blog Market:** Blog marketing is the process of reaching a business prospects through the use of a blog. Blog market is an act of positioning comments, expressing opinions or making announcement in a discussion forum and can be accomplished either by hosting your own blog or by posting comments and URL in other blogs related to your product or service online. Blog marketing may also help improve a Website's rankings in search results and is often used for search engine optimization (SEO) purposes.
- ✓ **B2B Portals:** B2B portals have set a new paradigm of competitiveness in the business world and it is the new age business model of the ever-changing business world. Some of the large -scale suppliers and buyers are heavily betting on it. With this boom in e-commerce and internet marketing, online Business-to-Business (B2B) portals and marketplaces are becoming much more prevalent. These B2B portals act as a bridge between buyers and sellers, importers and exporters, and offer them a common platform availing a bundle of some most useful services. No matter whether you are an exporter or importer, manufacturer or service provider, these online portals offer readymade lists of exporter and importers to help you quickly locate the exact item or company you are looking for.
- ✓ **Social-Media:** With the growth of Internet and smartphone penetration in India, The Social Media is touching large section of the society in many ways. The Social Media's adoption led by Facebook, Twitter and LinkedIn offers tremendous power to the marketers to do precise targeting in a very cost-efficient way. The best part of these platforms is they offer excellent reporting and analytics thus helping the executor to stay on top of campaign performance and take appropriate timely decisions to make the campaign more effective and result oriented.

MSMEs – Introduction:

Micro, Small and Medium Enterprises (MSME) sector has emerged as a highly vibrant and dynamic sector of the Indian economy over the last five decades. MSMEs not only play crucial role in providing large employment opportunities at comparatively lower capital cost than large industries but also help in industrialization of rural & backward areas, thereby, reducing regional imbalances, assuring more equitable distribution of national income and wealth. MSMEs are complementary to large industries as ancillary units and this sector contributes enormously to the socio-economic development of the country. The Sector consisting of

36 million units, as of today, provides employment to over 80 million persons. The Sector through more than 6,000 products contributes about 8% to GDP besides 45% to the total manufacturing output and 40% to the exports from the country. The MSME sector has the potential to spread industrial growth across the country and can be a major partner in the process of inclusive growth.

Source: MSME at a glance – 2017 - Ministry of Micro, Small and Medium Enterprises, Government of India

Micro, Small and Medium Enterprises (MSMEs) are the growth engines of our economy. In most countries, MSMEs constitute over 90% of enterprises. In addition, they contribute a major share to industrial production and exports besides creating employment opportunities. The Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD) reports that more than 95% of enterprises in the OECD area are MSMEs. In these countries, MSMEs account for almost 60% of private sector employment. According to a report by International Finance Corporation (IFC) that conducted a study across 132 countries, there are 125 million MSMEs with 85 million located in emerging economies. MSMEs have registered a growth of 6% between 2000-2009 globally, with Europe and Central Asia experiencing a growth of 15%. In India, MSMEs contribute significantly to production, exports and employment, thereby playing a significant role in the economic growth of the country. As per latest estimates, the sector contributes nearly 8% to the country's GDP, 45% to the manufactured output and 40% to the country's exports, while providing employment to 60 million people in more than 28.5 million enterprises.

Source: Empowering MSMEs through financing and linkages 2013 - Grant Thornton India LLP – Indian Chamber of Commerce

In India, the enterprises have been classified broadly into two categories:

- ✓ Manufacturing; and
- ✓ Those engaged in providing/rendering of services.

Both categories of enterprises have been further classified into micro, small and medium enterprises based on their investment in plant and machinery (for manufacturing enterprises) or on equipments (in case of enterprises providing or rendering services). The present ceiling on investment to be classified as micro, small or medium enterprises is as under

Source: Micro, Small and Medium Enterprises in India - An Overview - Development Commissioner (MSME) Government of India Ministry of Micro, Small & Medium Enterprises Nirman Bhavan, New Delhi-110 108 www.dcmsme.gov.in

Research Objectives:

- ✓ To determine the level of eMarketing used by MSMEs in Bangalore District B2B market and its contribution to marketing effectiveness;
- ✓ To identify the benefits of using eMarketing technology as marketing communication tool by MSMEs in Bangalore District B2B market;
- ✓ To establish factors influencing the use of eMarketing by MSMEs in Bangalore District B2B market;

Manufacturing Enterprises – Investment in Plant & Machinery		Service Enterprises – Investment in Equipments	
Micro	Up to Rs.25 Lakhs	Micro	Up to Rs. 10Lakhs
Small	above Rs. 25 Lakhs & upto Rs. 5 Crores	Small	above Rs. 10 Lakhs & upto Rs. 2 Crores
Med	above Rs. 5 Crores & upto Rs. 10 Crores	Med	above Rs. 2 Crores & upto Rs. 5 Crores

Hypothesis:

H0: There is no significant effect/impact of eMarketing on Micro, Small and Medium Enterprises (MSMEs) in the B2B market.

H1: There is a significant effect/impact of eMarketing on Micro, Small and Medium Enterprises (MSMEs) in the B2B market

Research Design and Methodology:

Research Design: The scope of this study constitutes the sample of 146 MSME units (micro, small and medium sized enterprises of Bangalore District). The directories used are KASSIA Directory, Karnataka State Industries Directory and Corel Directory as well as MSME databases from the relevant offices/associations like MSME-DI, PIA, ELCIA etc.,.

Type of Research: Descriptive

Sampling:

Population: Micro, Small and Medium Enterprises of Bangalore District

Sample Composition:

- ✓ Manufacturing Enterprises/Sector
- ✓ Service Enterprises/Sector

Sampling Technique: Convenience and judgemental Sampling

Sample Size: 146 out of which 136 usable questionnaires were considered for data analysis

Research Methodology: The study will take the form of descriptive research focusing on the usage level of e-marketing among MSMEs of Bangalore District, its benefits and factors influencing such usage. Careful

consideration has been given to the methodology adopted towards its purpose, strengths, weaknesses and the ability to meet the objectives of this study. Given the versatility nature of the area of study, the research questions are best pursued in the context of methodology of quantitative approach that utilizes the survey method.

As per the methodology, quantitative questionnaire has been deployed as a survey method. Now considering the research objectives:

- ✓ To determine the level of eMarketing used by MSMEs in Bangalore District B2B market and its contribution to marketing effectiveness;
- ✓ To identify the benefits of using eMarketing technology as marketing communication tool by MSMEs in Bangalore District B2B market;
- ✓ To establish factors influencing the use of eMarketing by MSMEs in Bangalore District B2B market;
- ✓ 1st, 2nd and 3rd are best addressed by utilising the survey method (quantitative questionnaire).

Data Presentation, Analysis and Interpretation:

This following data examines the analysis of the research data collected through survey research. The study aims to determine the level of eMarketing used by MSMEs in Bangalore District B2B market identifies the benefits of using eMarketing technology as marketing communication tool by MSMEs in Bangalore District B2B market and establishes the factors influencing the use of eMarketing by MSMEs in Bangalore District B2B market. In achieving these aims, the following data illustrates and discusses the descriptive analysis of the data to provide insights. The descriptive research represents completed questionnaires from MSMEs of Bangalore district.

E-Marketing Tools in the Enterprise:

From the following table we can observe that, about 89.0% of the respondents expressed that their enterprise uses e – marketing. Following bar chart also shows taller bar corresponding to the same.

Does Your Enterprise Uses e-Marketing?					
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Yes	121	89.0	89.0	89.0
	No	15	11.0	11.0	100.0
	Total	136	100.0	100.0	

From the following table we can observe that, about 88.2% of the respondents expressed that their enterprise has a website or a mobile application for marketing purposes. Following bar chart also shows taller bar corresponding to the same.

Does your enterprise have a website or a mobile application for marketing purposes?					
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Yes	120	88.2	88.2	88.2
	No	16	11.8	11.8	100.0
	Total	136	100.0	100.0	

From the following graph we can observe that, about 16.2% of the respondents expressed that they choose electronic mail for all the e – marketing resources/ tools. Following bar chart shows taller bar corresponding to the same.

From the following choose all the e-marketing resources/tools that your enterprise uses?

Does your enterprise have a website or a mobile application for marketing purposes?

Does your enterprise have a website or a mobile application for marketing purposes?

From the following table we can observe that, about 48.5% of the respondents expressed that they always use email marketing.

E-mail marketing					
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Always	66	48.5	48.5	48.5
	Frequently	29	21.3	21.3	69.9
	Occasionally	10	7.4	7.4	77.2
	Rarely	21	15.4	15.4	92.6
	Never	10	7.4	7.4	100.0
	Total	136	100.0	100.0	

From the following table we can observe that, about 44.9% of the respondents expressed that they always use SMS marketing.

SMS Marketing					
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Always	61	44.9	44.9	44.9
	Frequently	40	29.4	29.4	74.3
	Occasionally	22	16.2	16.2	90.4
	Rarely	6	4.4	4.4	94.9

	Never	7	5.1	5.1	100.0
	Total	136	100.0	100.0	

From the following table we can observe that, about 25.0% of the respondents expressed that they always use search engine marketing.

Search Engine Marketing					
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Always	34	25.0	25.0	25.0
	Frequently	32	23.5	23.5	48.5
	Occasionally	21	15.4	15.4	64.0
	Rarely	18	13.2	13.2	77.2
	Never	31	22.8	22.8	100.0
	Total	136	100.0	100.0	

From the following table we can observe that, about 27.2% of the respondents expressed that they frequently use online video marketing.

Online Video Marketing					
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Always	30	22.1	22.1	22.1
	Frequently	37	27.2	27.2	49.3
	Occasionally	19	14.0	14.0	63.2
	Rarely	19	14.0	14.0	77.2
	Never	31	22.8	22.8	100.0
	Total	136	100.0	100.0	

From the following table we can observe that, about 45.6% of the respondents expressed that they occasionally use blog marketing.

Blog Marketing					
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Always	1	.7	.7	.7
	Frequently	5	3.7	3.7	4.4
	Occasionally	62	45.6	45.6	50.0
	Rarely	59	43.4	43.4	93.4
	Never	9	6.6	6.6	100.0
	Total	136	100.0	100.0	

From the following table we can observe that, about 34.6% of the respondents expressed that they frequently use B2B portals marketing.

B2B Portals Marketing					
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Always	20	14.7	14.7	14.7
	Frequently	47	34.6	34.6	49.3
	Occasionally	29	21.3	21.3	70.6
	Rarely	22	16.2	16.2	86.8
	Never	18	13.2	13.2	100.0
	Total	136	100.0	100.0	

From the following table we can observe that, about 40.4% of the respondents expressed that they frequently use social media marketing.

Social Media Marketing					
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Always	19	14.0	14.0	14.0
	Frequently	55	40.4	40.4	54.4
	Occasionally	25	18.4	18.4	72.8
	Rarely	17	12.5	12.5	85.3
	Never	20	14.7	14.7	100.0
	Total	136	100.0	100.0	

From the following table we can observe that, about 46.3% of the respondents expressed that they never use E – directory marketing.

E-directory Marketing					
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Always	30	22.1	22.1	22.1
	Frequently	21	15.4	15.4	37.5

	Occasionally	5	3.7	3.7	41.2
	Rarely	17	12.5	12.5	53.7
	Never	63	46.3	46.3	100.0
	Total	136	100.0	100.0	

From the following table we can observe that, about 52.2% of the respondents expressed that they frequently use E – Banner advertisement on the internet.

E-banner advertisement on the internet					
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Always	3	2.2	2.2	2.2
	Frequently	5	3.7	3.7	5.9
	Occasionally	69	50.7	50.7	56.6
	Rarely	53	39.0	39.0	95.6
	Never	6	4.4	4.4	100.0
	Total	136	100.0	100.0	

Benefits of e-Marketing Tools in the Enterprise:

From the following table we can observe that, about 52.2% of the respondents expressed that convenience is important for using E – marketing.

Convenience					
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Very Important	31	22.8	22.8	22.8
	Important	71	52.2	52.2	75.0
	Moderately Important	6	4.4	4.4	79.4
	Slightly Important	16	11.8	11.8	91.2
	Not Important	12	8.8	8.8	100.0
	Total	136	100.0	100.0	

From the following table we can observe that, about 49.3% of the respondents expressed that market reach is very important for using E – marketing.

Market Reach					
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Very Important	67	49.3	49.3	49.3
	Important	46	33.8	33.8	83.1
	Moderately Important	2	1.5	1.5	84.6
	Slightly Important	12	8.8	8.8	93.4
	Not Important	9	6.6	6.6	100.0
	Total	136	100.0	100.0	

From the following table we can observe that, about 46.3% of the respondents expressed that cost effectiveness is important for using E – marketing.

Cost-Effectiveness					
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Very Important	45	33.1	33.1	33.1
	Important	63	46.3	46.3	79.4
	Moderately Important	3	2.2	2.2	81.6
	Slightly Important	13	9.6	9.6	91.2
	Not Important	12	8.8	8.8	100.0
	Total	136	100.0	100.0	

From the following table we can observe that, about 47.1% of the respondents expressed that effective communication is important for using E – marketing.

Effective in Communication					
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Very Important	20	14.7	14.7	14.7
	Important	64	47.1	47.1	61.8
	Moderately Important	29	21.3	21.3	83.1
	Slightly Important	12	8.8	8.8	91.9
	Not Important	11	8.1	8.1	100.0
	Total	136	100.0	100.0	

From the following table we can observe that, about 50.0% of the respondents expressed that customer engagement is very important for using E – marketing.

Customer Engagement					
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		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Very Important	68	50.0	50.0	50.0
	Important	39	28.7	28.7	78.7
	Moderately Important	4	2.9	2.9	81.6
	Slightly Important	14	10.3	10.3	91.9
	Not Important	11	8.1	8.1	100.0
	Total	136	100.0	100.0	

From the following table we can observe that, about 43.4% of the respondents expressed that accessible at any time of the day is important for using E – marketing.

Accessible at any time of the day					
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Very Important	20	14.7	14.7	14.7
	Important	59	43.4	43.4	58.1
	Moderately Important	34	25.0	25.0	83.1
	Slightly Important	14	10.3	10.3	93.4
	Not Important	9	6.6	6.6	100.0
	Total	136	100.0	100.0	

From the following table we can observe that, about 31.6% of the respondents expressed that build brand awareness is important for using E – marketing.

Builds Brand Awareness					
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Very Important	26	19.1	19.1	19.1
	Important	43	31.6	31.6	50.7
	Moderately Important	37	27.2	27.2	77.9
	Slightly Important	19	14.0	14.0	91.9
	Not Important	11	8.1	8.1	100.0
	Total	136	100.0	100.0	

From the following table we can observe that, about 33.8% of the respondents expressed that increase credibility is important for using E – marketing.

Increase credibility					
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Very Important	26	19.1	19.1	19.1
	Important	46	33.8	33.8	52.9
	Moderately Important	35	25.7	25.7	78.7
	Slightly Important	17	12.5	12.5	91.2
	Not Important	12	8.8	8.8	100.0
	Total	136	100.0	100.0	

From the following table we can observe that, about 35.3% of the respondents expressed that lead conversions is slightly important for using E – marketing.

Lead Conversions					
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Very Important	19	14.0	14.0	14.0
	Important	25	18.4	18.4	32.4
	Moderately Important	33	24.3	24.3	56.6
	Slightly Important	48	35.3	35.3	91.9
	Not Important	11	8.1	8.1	100.0
	Total	136	100.0	100.0	

From the following table we can observe that, about 47.1% of the respondents expressed that obtain key performance metrics is important for using E – marketing.

Obtain Key Performance Metrics					
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Very Important	53	39.0	39.0	39.0
	Important	64	47.1	47.1	86.0
	Moderately Important	2	1.5	1.5	87.5
	Slightly Important	9	6.6	6.6	94.1
	Not Important	8	5.9	5.9	100.0
	Total	136	100.0	100.0	

From the following table we can observe that, about 64.0% of the respondents agreed that E – marketing helps increase the number of clients.

E-marketing helps increase the number of clients					
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Strongly Agree	30	22.1	22.1	22.1
	Agree	87	64.0	64.0	86.0
	Neutral	2	1.5	1.5	87.5
	Disagree	8	5.9	5.9	93.4
	Strongly Disagree	9	6.6	6.6	100.0
	Total	136	100.0	100.0	

From the following table we can observe that, about 39.7% of the respondents agreed that E – marketing helps increase sales.

E-Marketing Helps Increase Sales					
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Strongly Agree	14	10.3	10.3	10.3
	Agree	54	39.7	39.7	50.0
	Neutral	47	34.6	34.6	84.6
	Disagree	14	10.3	10.3	94.9
	Strongly Disagree	7	5.1	5.1	100.0
	Total	136	100.0	100.0	

From the following table we can observe that, about 41.9% of the respondents agreed that E – marketing helps increase profits.

E-Marketing Helps Increase Profits					
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Strongly Agree	23	16.9	16.9	16.9
	Agree	57	41.9	41.9	58.8
	Neutral	41	30.1	30.1	89.0
	Disagree	8	5.9	5.9	94.9
	Strongly Disagree	7	5.1	5.1	100.0
	Total	136	100.0	100.0	

From the following table we can observe that, about 71.3% of the respondents disagreed that E – marketing helps increase competitiveness in the market.

E-marketing helps increase competitiveness in the market					
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Strongly Agree	6	4.4	4.4	4.4
	Agree	5	3.7	3.7	8.1
	Neutral	14	10.3	10.3	18.4
	Disagree	97	71.3	71.3	89.7
	Strongly Disagree	14	10.3	10.3	100.0
	Total	136	100.0	100.0	

From the following table we can observe that, about 52.2% of the respondents expressed that Email marketing is slightly effective.

E-Mail Marketing					
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Not at all Effective	6	4.4	4.4	4.4
	Slightly Effective	13	9.6	9.6	14.0
	Moderately Effective	26	19.1	19.1	33.1
	Very Effective	71	52.2	52.2	85.3
	Extremely Effective	20	14.7	14.7	100.0
	Total	136	100.0	100.0	

From the following table we can observe that, about 36.0% of the respondents expressed that SMS marketing is slightly effective.

SMS Marketing					
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Not at all Effective	8	5.9	5.9	5.9
	Slightly Effective	38	27.9	27.9	33.8
	Moderately Effective	30	22.1	22.1	55.9
	Very Effective	49	36.0	36.0	91.9
	Total	136	100.0	100.0	

	Extremely Effective	11	8.1	8.1	100.0
	Total	136	100.0	100.0	

From the following table we can observe that, about 42.6% of the respondents expressed that search engine marketing is very effective.

Search Engine Marketing					
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Not at all Effective	10	7.4	7.4	7.4
	Slightly Effective	18	13.2	13.2	20.6
	Moderately Effective	17	12.5	12.5	33.1
	Very Effective	58	42.6	42.6	75.7
	Extremely Effective	33	24.3	24.3	100.0
	Total	136	100.0	100.0	

From the following table we can observe that, about 39.0% of the respondents expressed that online video marketing is very effective.

Online Video Marketing					
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Not at all Effective	6	4.4	4.4	4.4
	Slightly Effective	19	14.0	14.0	18.4
	Moderately Effective	19	14.0	14.0	32.4
	Very Effective	53	39.0	39.0	71.3
	Extremely Effective	39	28.7	28.7	100.0
	Total	136	100.0	100.0	

From the following table we can observe that, about 41.9% of the respondents expressed that online video marketing is slightly effective.

Blog Marketing					
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Not at all Effective	9	6.6	6.6	6.6
	Slightly Effective	57	41.9	41.9	48.5
	Moderately Effective	27	19.9	19.9	68.4
	Very Effective	24	17.6	17.6	86.0
	Extremely Effective	19	14.0	14.0	100.0
	Total	136	100.0	100.0	

From the following table we can observe that, about 37.5% of the respondents expressed that blog marketing is very effective.

B2B Portals Marketing					
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Slightly Effective	21	15.4	15.4	15.4
	Moderately Effective	38	27.9	27.9	43.4
	Very Effective	51	37.5	37.5	80.9
	Extremely Effective	26	19.1	19.1	100.0
	Total	136	100.0	100.0	

From the following table we can observe that, about 31.6% of the respondents expressed that B2B portals marketing is moderately effective.

Social Media Marketing					
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Not at all Effective	6	4.4	4.4	4.4
	Slightly Effective	36	26.5	26.5	30.9
	Moderately Effective	43	31.6	31.6	62.5
	Very Effective	34	25.0	25.0	87.5
	Extremely Effective	17	12.5	12.5	100.0
	Total	136	100.0	100.0	

From the following table we can observe that, about 44.9% of the respondents expressed that social media marketing is moderately effective.

E-Directory Marketing					
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Not at all Effective	19	14.0	14.0	14.0
	Slightly Effective	23	16.9	16.9	30.9
	Moderately Effective	3	2.2	2.2	33.1

	Very Effective	30	22.1	22.1	55.1
	Extremely Effective	61	44.9	44.9	100.0
	Total	136	100.0	100.0	

From the following table we can observe that, about 47.8% of the respondents expressed that E banner advertisement on the internet is slightly effective.

E-banner advertisement on the internet					
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Not at all Effective	45	33.1	33.1	33.1
	Slightly Effective	65	47.8	47.8	80.9
	Moderately Effective	10	7.4	7.4	88.2
	Very Effective	3	2.2	2.2	90.4
	Extremely Effective	13	9.6	9.6	100.0
	Total	136	100.0	100.0	

Factors that Influence Adoption of e-Marketing Tools in the Enterprise:

From the following table we can observe that, about 40.4% of the respondents agreed that perceived benefits of e-marketing technology promote its adoption.

Perceived benefits of e-marketing technology promote its adoption.					
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Strongly Agree	36	26.5	26.5	26.5
	Agree	55	40.4	40.4	66.9
	Neutral	3	2.2	2.2	69.1
	Disagree	23	16.9	16.9	86.0
	Strongly Disagree	19	14.0	14.0	100.0
	Total	136	100.0	100.0	

From the following table we can observe that, about 47.8% of the respondents agreed that cost considerations of e-marketing technology affect its adoption.

Cost considerations of e-marketing technology affect its adoption.					
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Strongly Agree	12	8.8	8.8	8.8
	Agree	65	47.8	47.8	56.6
	Neutral	46	33.8	33.8	90.4
	Disagree	8	5.9	5.9	96.3
	Strongly Disagree	5	3.7	3.7	100.0
	Total	136	100.0	100.0	

From the following table we can observe that, about 54.4% of the respondents agreed that perceived compatibility of e-marketing technology promotes its adoption.

Perceived compatibility of e-marketing technology promotes its adoption.					
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Strongly Agree	39	28.7	28.7	28.7
	Agree	74	54.4	54.4	83.1
	Neutral	9	6.6	6.6	89.7
	Disagree	8	5.9	5.9	95.6
	Strongly Disagree	6	4.4	4.4	100.0
	Total	136	100.0	100.0	

From the following table we can observe that, about 59.6% of the respondents agreed that perceived ease of use of e-marketing technology is positively associated with its adoption.

Perceived ease of use of e-marketing technology is positively associated with its adoption					
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Strongly Agree	32	23.5	23.5	23.5
	Agree	81	59.6	59.6	83.1
	Neutral	12	8.8	8.8	91.9
	Disagree	6	4.4	4.4	96.3
	Strongly Disagree	5	3.7	3.7	100.0
	Total	136	100.0	100.0	

From the following table we can observe that, about 45.6% of the respondents were neutral about competitive pressure leads to adoption of e-marketing tools.

Competitive pressure leads to adoption of e-marketing tools					
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent

Valid	Strongly Agree	10	7.4	7.4	7.4
	Agree	22	16.2	16.2	23.5
	Neutral	62	45.6	45.6	69.1
	Disagree	35	25.7	25.7	94.9
	Strongly Disagree	7	5.1	5.1	100.0
	Total	136	100.0	100.0	

From the following table we can observe that, about 61.0% of the respondents agreed that external support helps in adoption of e-marketing tools.

External support helps in adoption of e-marketing tools					
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Strongly Agree	28	20.6	20.6	20.6
	Agree	83	61.0	61.0	81.6
	Neutral	11	8.1	8.1	89.7
	Disagree	7	5.1	5.1	94.9
	Strongly Disagree	7	5.1	5.1	100.0
	Total	136	100.0	100.0	

From the following table we can observe that, about 36.8% of the respondents were neutral about customers' pressure leads to adoption of e-marketing tools.

Customers' pressure leads to adoption of e-marketing tools					
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Strongly Agree	5	3.7	3.7	3.7
	Agree	50	36.8	36.8	40.4
	Neutral	49	36.0	36.0	76.5
	Disagree	26	19.1	19.1	95.6
	Strongly Disagree	6	4.4	4.4	100.0
	Total	136	100.0	100.0	

From the following table we can observe that, about 51.5% of the respondents agreed that pressure from suppliers forces adoption of e-marketing tools.

Pressure from suppliers forces adoption of e-marketing tools					
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Strongly Agree	48	35.3	35.3	35.3
	Agree	70	51.5	51.5	86.8
	Neutral	5	3.7	3.7	90.4
	Disagree	5	3.7	3.7	94.1
	Strongly Disagree	8	5.9	5.9	100.0
	Total	136	100.0	100.0	

From the following table we can observe that, about 36.0% of the respondents agreed that infrastructure availability in the organisation, favours adoption of e-marketing tools.

Infrastructure availability in the organisation, favours adoption of e-marketing tools					
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Strongly Agree	12	8.8	8.8	8.8
	Agree	49	36.0	36.0	44.9
	Neutral	9	6.6	6.6	51.5
	Disagree	63	46.3	46.3	97.8
	Strongly Disagree	3	2.2	2.2	100.0
	Total	136	100.0	100.0	

From the following table we can observe that, about 55.1% of the respondents agreed that size of the firm is positively related with the adoption of e-marketing tools.

Size of the firm is positively related with the adoption of e-marketing tools					
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Strongly Agree	48	35.3	35.3	35.3
	Agree	75	55.1	55.1	90.4
	Neutral	2	1.5	1.5	91.9
	Disagree	6	4.4	4.4	96.3
	Strongly Disagree	5	3.7	3.7	100.0
	Total	136	100.0	100.0	

From the following table we can observe that, about 56.6% of the respondents agreed that the larger the number of skilled workforce in the organisation, the easier is the adoption of e-marketing tools.

The larger the number of skilled workforce in the organisation, the easier is the adoption of e-marketing tools					
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Strongly Agree	44	32.4	32.4	32.4
	Agree	77	56.6	56.6	89.0
	Neutral	1	.7	.7	89.7
	Disagree	7	5.1	5.1	94.9
	Strongly Disagree	7	5.1	5.1	100.0
	Total	136	100.0	100.0	

From the following table we can observe that, about 51.5% of the respondents agreed that the openness of organisational culture towards change and innovation eases the adoption of e-marketing tools.

The openness of organisational culture towards change and innovation eases the adoption of e-marketing tools					
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Strongly Agree	58	42.6	42.6	42.6
	Agree	70	51.5	51.5	94.1
	Neutral	1	.7	.7	94.9
	Disagree	4	2.9	2.9	97.8
	Strongly Disagree	3	2.2	2.2	100.0
	Total	136	100.0	100.0	

From the following table we can observe that, about 56.6% of the respondents agreed that the degree of understanding of the owner/top managers with regards to e-marketing tools determines its adoption.

The degree of understanding of the owner/top managers with regards to e-marketing tools determines its adoption					
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Strongly Agree	56	41.2	41.2	41.2
	Agree	77	56.6	56.6	97.8
	Disagree	3	2.2	2.2	100.0
	Total	136	100.0	100.0	

From the following table we can observe that, about 55.9% of the respondents agreed that experience of the owner/top managers with e-marketing tools influences its adoption.

Experience of the owner/top managers with e-marketing tools influences its adoption					
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Strongly Agree	56	41.2	41.2	41.2
	Agree	76	55.9	55.9	97.1
	Disagree	3	2.2	2.2	99.3
	Strongly Disagree	1	.7	.7	100.0
	Total	136	100.0	100.0	

Testing of Hypothesis:

In order test the hypothesis a one-way analysis of variance was applied by using SPSS.

ANOVA					
	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Groups	8.168	2	4.084	37.585	.000
Within Groups	14.452	133	.109		
Total	22.620	135			

The F value corresponding to the mean difference in B2B market between the micro, medium and small enterprises was 37.585 and its corresponding p value is 0.000<0.05. Since the p value is less than 0.05, we can conclude that there is a significant effect/impact of eMarketing on Micro, Small and Medium Enterprises (MSMEs) in the B2B market.

Summary of Findings, Suggestions and Conclusion:

Major Findings:

Overall 36% of micro, 42% of small and 20% medium enterprises are covered for the study among MSMEs of Bangalore District. 64% are from manufacturing sector and 35% are from service sector. The targeted respondents are majorly marketing/sales-in-charge of the firms followed by proprietors, managing directors and directors among the enterprises covered for the study.

E-marketing has a significant effectiveness on Micro, Small and Medium Enterprises (MSMEs) in B2B market of Bangalore District. Major findings from the study are: 89.0% of the respondents expressed that their

enterprise uses e – marketing. About 88.2% of the respondents expressed that their enterprises have a website or a mobile application for marketing purposes.

Among the marketing tools ie., e-mail, SMS, Search Engine, Online Video, Blog, B2B Portals, Social Media, E-directory and E-Banner about 16.2% of the respondents expressed that they choose electronic mail compare to all other e – marketing resources/ tools. In terms of usage of e-marketing tools e-mail, SMS and Search Engine takes the highest usage rate of more 53% cumulative percentage.

With regard to the benefits of using e-marketing the highest ratings are given to: Obtain key performance metrics, market reach, cost-effectiveness, customer engagement compares to other benefits viz., effective in communication, Accessible at any point of time, builds brand awareness, increase credibility and lead conversions. The most respondents agree that e-marketing helps in increase of number of clients and increases the profits compare to other variable like increases the sales or competitiveness in the market.

On the degree of effectiveness of e-marketing tools considered for the study among MSMEs it is observed that, e-mail, search engine, E-directory are most effective compare to other tools like blog, SMS, Social Media, E-banner, B2B etc.,

Among the factors influencing the adoption of e-marketing tools among the MSMEs ie., Technological, Market Environmental, Organizational, Individual factors the following are determinants are perceived to be true:

On the technological front compatibility of e-marketing technology and perceived ease of use of e-marketing technology are highest determinants for adoption of e-marketing in MSMEs. On the environmental front pressure from suppliers and external support are the factors most influencing the adoption of e-marketing among MSMEs. On the organizational front openness of organizational culture towards the change and innovation and size of the firm is perceived to be most influential factors among others.

Whereas on the individual front the degree of understanding of the owner/top managers with regard to e-marketing tools and experience of the owner/top managers equally determines the adoption of e-marketing among MSMEs.

Recommendations:

The study identifies the effectiveness of usage level of e-marketing and its tools by MSMEs, the benefits derived by the MSMEs in effective use of e-marketing and the factors that influence its adoption and therefore researcher recommends that policy makers and government should ensure that grants; subsidies and loans are made available to MSMEs to be able to effectively adopt E-marketing technology. Public education programmes should be put in place to ensure that individuals and businesses are made aware of the potentials and benefits of E-marketing adoption.

There should be training on e-marketing tools usage to owners of MSME sector about the effective use of modern e-marketing tools and its advantages. The owners who believe in conventional / traditional marketing should change their mindset to adopt internet marketing effectively with learning. Everyone should learn to use this effective media of communication, there are still many owners in MSME sector who still believe in traditional marketing. The researcher recommends the emerging entrepreneurs in the market to explore the modern tools to reach the market globally. Dedicate time to learn how e-marketing tools works. Discover their core e-marketing tools which suits to their type of business, track and measure the effectiveness of ROI. Electronic marketing can be easy and affordable if MSMEs follow the right practices and present their business in front of potential customers by using the right tools. MSMEs can make their mark on this massive landscape by being innovative and unique. It is essential for MSMEs to harness the advantages that this technology. E-marketing has many things to offer for a small business, especially with respect to marketing processes. It is also a way to differentiate from competitors. In order to scale-up a small firm has this opportunity to expand its business worldwide by availing the benefits of e-marketing and grow bigger.

Conclusion:

The study found that use of e-marketing and its tools has its significant effectiveness on the performance of their firms. MSMEs are able to reap the benefits of e-marketing tools effectively to improve their customer relations through the use of e-marketing tools and as well keep the track of their performance metrics. The market reach has increased with cost-effective customer engagements. It is evident from the study that e-marketing has helped the MSMEs to increase the clients and profits. Ease of use of e-marketing tools and its compatibility on the technological front are some the most influential factors and openness to organizational culture and degree of understanding of owners towards power of e-marketing are playing the major perceived roles among environmental and individual factors towards adoption of e-marketing in MSMEs of Bangalore District.

Suggestions for the Further Study:

There is a need for further study on the knowledge of e-marketing tools among MSME owners because of its dynamic nature and rapid technological changes/advancements taking place on day-to-day basis on this powerful media of internet. Pursuant to this there is also a need for understanding the challenges faced by the MSMEs in understanding the effectiveness of e-marketing tools.

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